

OBSERVATION OF STATIC STRENGTH AND FATIGUE LIFE OF REPAIRED GRAPHITE/EPOXY USING TENSILE COUPON

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SUMMARY: The static strength and fatigue life of repaired graphite/epoxy laminates are observed using tensile coupon. The lay-up of investigated laminates was $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$. Static strength was measured from the specimens prepared by various repair techniques such as precured-single patch, precured-double patch and cure-in-place methods. The strength was recovered to the extent of 60-80% of unnotched case. Fatigue life was also measured from the laminates repaired with cure-in-place method. Hwang and Han's MFLPE 1(modified fatigue life prediction equation 1), which was based on the fatigue modulus degradation model and reference modulus, was chosen for fatigue life prediction of repaired specimen and compared with the conventional fatigue life equations such as S-N curve and Basquin's relation. The MFLPE 1 has better agreement with experimental data than S-N curve and Basquin's relation.

KEYWORDS: repaired graphite/epoxy laminates, repaired graphite/epoxy laminates, fatigue modulus, fatigue life prediction equation

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials, especially on the aircraft, have been expanding in recent years because of their superior strength-to-weight, stiffness-to-weight ratios and better fatigue resistance compared to the other materials. But unfortunately, most composite materials may contain defects such as cracks, voids and delaminations produced by either fatigue, impact damage or poor design. These defects may cause a bad influence on the various functional capabilities.

To restore a damaged part's structural integrity, attention has recently been focused on developing repair procedures [1, 2]. Considerable effort has been devoted to the development of generic repair technology for advanced composites with aircraft companies as the central figures, but the repair standards are not established yet [3-5]. Some repair designs and application procedures have little chance of success, and in many cases service lives of components have been reduced by poor design.

To establish repair standards, the behavior of repaired composites must be observed not only under static but fatigue loading. In this study, the static and fatigue behavior of repaired composites is observed and analyzed.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The fatigue modulus, F , proposed by Hwang and Han[6, 7] is defined as a function of loading cycle, n , and applied stress, q .

$$F(n, q) = \frac{\sigma_a}{\varepsilon(n)} = \sigma_u \frac{q}{\varepsilon(n)} \quad (1)$$

where F is fatigue modulus, σ_a is applied stress, ε is resultant strain, σ_u is ultimate strength and q is ratio of applied stress to ultimate strength. Initial and final conditions give the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned} F(0, q) &= F_0 = E_0 \\ F(N, q) &= F_f \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Fatigue modulus at 0th cycle, F_0 , is assumed to be the same as elastic modulus, E_0 , and fatigue modulus at fracture is defined as F_f at the number of cycles to failure, N . It is reasonable to assume that applied stress has a linear relation with resultant strain at any arbitrary loading cycle if the specimen undergoes constant maximum loading. This assumption follows:

$$\sigma_a = F(n)\varepsilon(n) \quad (3)$$

The fatigue modulus degradation rate at any fatigue cycle can be assumed as a power function of a number of fatigue cycles and the fatigue modulus itself,

$$\frac{dF}{dn} = -A \frac{Cn^{C-1}}{BF^{B-1}} \quad (4)$$

where A , B , and C are material constants. Integration of Equation(4) by substituting the condition (2) gives

$$F_f^B - F_0^B = -AN^C \quad (5)$$

The reference modulus, F_R , is assumed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_0 / F_R &= p \\ F_f / F_R &= f(q) = q \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where p and q are material constants and applied stress level, respectively. Substituting Equation (6) into Equation (5), one obtains

$$N = [M(p^B - q^B)]^{1/C} \quad (7)$$

Using the above equation, fatigue life of materials can be predicted as long as the material constants M , B , C , and p are known[8]

EXPERIMENTAL

The parent laminate was fabricated with a stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$. The prepreg tape manufactured by Han Kook Fiber Company was used. A circular hole was made at the center of each specimen using drilling machine. Four different holes with radii 1, 2, 3 and 4 mm were chosen for static tests and three different holes with radii 1, 3 and 4 mm were chosen for fatigue tests. The width of test laminate was 25 mm and thickness was 1mm. The fatigue test specimen configuration is presented in Figure 1. Static tests were conducted for the specimens repaired by following repair methods. Fatigue tests were performed in load control mode using a sinusoidal wave form with frequency 3Hz which is considered to give a negligible temperature rise during tests.

Cosmetic Treatment

The hole was filled with epoxy which was mixed with chopped graphite fiber and cured in room temperature.

Precured-Single/Double Patch

The patch that had the same lay-up with parent laminate was adhered to the damaged area with adhesive (2216B/A) manufactured by 3M Company. The width of patch was the same as the parent laminate, and the length was 40 mm for single patch and 40 and 60 mm for double patch.

Cure-in-Place Patch

Prepreg was laid up in order of $0^\circ, -45^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 0° from parent laminate with varying the length by 30, 40, 50 and 60 mm, respectively. To reduce the stress concentration at the end of the outer layer of reinforced patch, the outer patch was cut in saw shape[9].

Figure 1. Fatigue test specimen configuration (cure-in-place)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile strength of parent laminate was found to be 608 MPa. Static test results are summarized in table 1. Non-patch method(filling) does not show reinforcing effect, while all patch methods show good results.

The strength recovery to the unnotched tensile strength for various repair methods is presented in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 2 is the case when the flaw size was 2 mm and Figure 3 is when the flaw size was 4 mm. Precured-double patch and cure-in-place patch methods show good results. In both cases, the tensile strength was recovered to the extent of about 60-80% of unnotched tensile strength. As flaw size increases, repaired strength degradation rate decrease more than notched strength degradation rate. In other words, the repair is more effective for large damage than for small damage. From above static test results, it could be concluded that cure-in-place method was the most effective one because it was good for strength recovery and caused minimum weight increase.

For the fatigue test results of repaired specimens, fatigue life was predicted by S-N curve, Basquin's relation and H and H's MFLPE 1. S-N curve and Basquin's relation can be written as follows:

$$\text{S-N curve} \quad q = k \log N + d \quad (8.a)$$

$$\text{Basquin's relation} \quad \sigma_a = \sigma_f' (2N) \quad (8.b)$$

where, N is the fatigue life, σ_a is applied stress and q is applied stress level ($=\sigma_a / \sigma_u$).

To compare the accuracy of these prediction equations, the SSR(residual sum of square) was defined as follows.

$$SSR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\log N_{exp} - \log N_{cal})^2 \quad (9)$$

Table 1. Static test results (MPa)

Radius(mm)	1	2	3	4
Notched	445	373	335	298
Fill	-	369	-	303
Precured Single patch(40mm)	-	401	-	360
Precured Double Patch(40mm)	-	464	-	393
Precured Double Patch(60mm)	-	526	-	512
Cure-in-place Double Patch	-	-	-	451
Cure-in-place Single Patch	466	426	412	377

where N_{exp} is experimental data, N_{cal} is fatigue life predicted by life equations, and n is the number of data.

Figure 2. Strength recovery of various repair methods($r=2mm$)

Figure 3. Strength recovery of various repair methods($r=4mm$)

Table 2. Material constants and SSR

Radius(mm)		1	3	4
MFLPE 1	p	0.974	1.091	1.005
	M	353.62	60.03	50.40
	B	2.672	0.158	0.993
	C	0.361	0.110	0.180
	SSR	0.1842	0.1943	0.1680
Basquin's relation	σ_f'	518.18	409.09	413.22
	b	-0.017	-0.019	-0.022
	SSR	0.9784	0.3369	0.3416
S-N curve	k	-0.0324	-0.0370	-0.0440
	d	1.0386	0.9720	1.0594
	SSR	0.7827	0.3129	0.3011

Figure 4. Comparison of MFLPE 1, S-N curve and Basquin's relation($r=1\text{mm}$)

Figure 5. Comparison of MFLPE 1, S-N curve and Basquin's relation($r=3\text{mm}$)

Figure 6. Comparison of MFLPE 1, S-N curve and Basquin's relation($r=4\text{mm}$)

Figure 7. Comparison of fatigue life of unnotched, repaired and notched laminate($r=1mm$)

Figure 8. Comparison of fatigue life of unnotched, repaired and notched laminate($r=3mm$)

Figure 9. Comparison of fatigue life of unnotched, repaired and notched laminate($r=4mm$)

Table 2 presents material constants and SSR of life prediction equations. The value of SSR is smaller when predicted with MFLPE 1 than when predicted with other life prediction equations, regardless of flaw size. The prediction results are compared with experimental data in Figures 4, 5 and 6 in the case of radius 1, 3 and 4 mm, respectively. The comparison shows that fatigue life of repaired composite laminates could be predicted much better by MFLPE 1 than by S-N Curve or Basquin's relation.

Flaw size effect on the repair was observed by comparing fatigue life of unnotched, notched and repaired laminates. The comparison is presented in Figures 7, 8 and 9 which is the case of radius 1, 3 and 4 mm respectively. In all cases, repaired laminates exhibits higher fatigue strength. One possible explanation of this lies in the higher effective stiffness resulting from load distribution by reinforcing patch. From these figures, one can find that as flaw size increases, the repair efficiency increases, which is same as static cases.

FSRF (fatigue strength reduction factor) was defined to consider the fatigue strength degradation rate

$$FSRF = \frac{\frac{FS_{notched}}{FS_{unnotched}}}{\frac{FS_{repaired}}{FS_{unnotched}}} \quad (10)$$

where $FS_{notched}$ is fatigue strength of notched composites at N_i cycles, $FS_{unnotched}$ is fatigue strength of unnotched composites at N_i cycles, and $FS_{repaired}$ is fatigue strength of repaired composites at N_i cycles. Arbitrary fatigue cycles ($N_1=50$ cycles, $N_2=2500$ cycles, $N_3=125000$ cycles) were chosen to observe the behavior of repaired composites. Figure 10 shows the comparison of FSRF at each arbitrary cycle. At high cycle region (N_3), repaired fatigue strength reduced more than at low cycle region (N_1). It is considered that these phenomena are caused by the failure modes of repaired composites.

Figure 10. Fatigue strength reduction factor

As fatigue loading cycle progresses, the cure-in-place patch debonded one by one from outer side gradually, and finally debonded entirely from parent laminate about at the mid-cycle of

fatigue life. As a results, fatigue strength degradation rate increases rapidly, so that at high cycle region, fatigue strength increase less than at low cycle region regardless of flaw sizes.

CONCLUSION

Cure-in-place method was found the most effective repair method among a variety of relatively thin laminate repair methods. Static and fatigue strength were restored more as flaw size increases. It was found that MFLPE 1 predicts fatigue life of repaired composites better than conventional S-N curve and Basquin's relation.

REFERENCES

1. Middleton, D. H., *Composite Materials in Aircraft Structures*, Longman, 1990
2. Jones, J. S. and Graves, S. R., "Repair Techniques for Celion /LARC-16 Graphite /Polyimide Composite Structures," NASA CR-3794 ,1984
3. Myhre, S. H., "Advanced Composite Repair-Recent Development and Some Problems," *Composite Repair*, SAMPE Monograph No.1, 1985, pp. 14-25
4. Shyprykevich, P., "Standardization of Composite repair for Commercial Transport Aircraft," *Proceedings of Composite Repair of Aircraft Structures*, 1995, pp. 1-24
5. Davis, M.J., "A Call for Minimum Standards in Design and Application Technology for Bonded Structural Repairs," Int. Symposium on Composite Repair of Aircraft Structure, 1995
6. Hwang, W. and Han, K. S., "Fatigue of Composite - Fatigue Modulus Concept and life Prediction," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.20, 1986, pp. 154-165
7. Hwang, W. and Han, K. S., "Fatigue of Composite Materials - Damage Model and Life Prediction," *Composite materials :Fatigue and Fracture* (Second volume) , ASTM STP 1012, Paul A. Lagace, Ed., 1989, pp. 87-102
8. Hwang, W., Lee, C. S., Park, H. C., and Han, K. S., "Single- and Multi-Stress Level Fatigue Life Prediction of Glass/ Epoxy Composites," *Journal of Advanced Materials*, July 1995, pp. 3-9
9. Stone, R. H., "Development of Repair Procedures for Graphite/Epoxy Structures on Commercial Transport," *Composite Repairs*, SAMPE Monograph No.1 , 1985, pp. 26-39